

Title: Machine Learning - Make notion simple and practical.

Name: Dr. Ganesh Bhokare

Affiliation: iDLVision, Consultant - Computer Vision and Machine Learning, Pune, MH, India.

INTRODUCTION:

The Machine Learning is a science of emulating human intelligence in computers by means of algorithms to classify and predict objects based on real world data captured by various sensors such as camera, LiDAR, RADAR, microphones etc. It offers sub-optimal intelligence to machines that is computers to support human life right from simple assistance in home appliances, mobile phones, physically disabled people to most advance technology of video surveillance, autonomous vehicles and military applications. Basically, at high level, it is implementation of statistical models used for segmentation, detection, classification, recognition and prediction of data captured by sensors. These models are nothing but mathematical equations and PDF (Probability Distribution functions). The parameters of models are estimated using techniques of ML(Maximum Likelihood), MAP(Maximum A Priori) or Bayes estimation based on given data known as supervised training, Once the optimal model is determined, it is used in the process inference - segmentation, detection, classification etc.

AIM:

To conceive the notion of Machine Learning and explore its applications in video surveillance and automobile - ADAS (Advance Driving Assistance Systems) and Autonomous vehicles.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

1. Segmentation: In this operations surrounding world captured by sensors such as camera is divided into various regions based on some criteria such as textures, colors, objects etc.
2. Detection: Once regions are segmented, the objects on segments are detected which can be humans, animals, vehicles, roads buildings etc.
3. Classifier: Once objects are detected they are classified. For example, detected objects are classified as cyclist, bikers, trucks.
4. Recognition: Classified objects can be further recognized as person, human emotions, vehicle makes, number plates.
5. Prediction: Prediction is a process in which outputs are continuous such as next position of vehicles, weather forecasting etc.

RESULTS:

MATLAB simulations shows results for segmentation, detection, recognition, classification and regression.

CONCLUSIONS:

The MATLAB simulation results shows how human intelligence is implemented in computers and their applications in video surveillance and automobile - ADAS and Autonomous vehicles.

KEYWORDS:

Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Supervised Learning, Unsupervised Learning, Semi-supervised Learning, ADAS, Autonomous vehicles, RADAR, LiDAR.

BIOGRAPHY:

Dr. Ganesh Bhokare, has completed his Master and Ph.D. in Signal Processing from IIT, Mumbai, India. He is having 20+ years of industries experience in design, architect and development of real time Signal Processing Computer Vision and Machine/Deep Learning algorithms in C/C++ and MATLAB on heterogeneous embedded multi-core platforms.